

FOUR OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS STAGE

Karimova Jahona

1st stage master of Tashkent State
Pedagogical University named after Nizami

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Abstract. *the article shows that the overall algorithm for creating an educational space for aesthetic education of elementary school students consists of four stages, and the author's conclusions on aesthetic education of students are presented.*

Keywords: *aesthetic education, elementary school students, literary reading, visual arts, music, seeing and understanding the beauty of the world, artistic-aesthetic taste, artistic-aesthetic education.*

In the system of aesthetic and creative education of primary school students, a special place is given to "art" subjects. The main role in the aesthetic education of elementary school students is given to subjects such as literary reading, fine arts and music, because they help in the formation of aesthetic ideas among young students, their artistic standards, aesthetic attitude to reality and creativity. plays a decisive role in Aesthetic education helps young students to identify the positive aspects of each subject, understand its importance and love the subject [1]. The ability to see and understand the beauty of the world around us, helps to develop emotional culture, artistic-aesthetic taste, work and creative activity, develops a sense of determination, mutual support and the creative self of a person makes it possible to understand.

In accordance with the curriculum of the general secondary education institution; can be represented by programs of extracurricular activities, optional courses, study groups and excursion activities. It is important to create pedagogical conditions for aesthetic education of young students [2].

The overall algorithm for creating an educational space for aesthetic education of elementary school students consists of four stages:

First stage: determination of aesthetic needs. At this stage, children should be given aesthetic education in a general secondary educational institution, in which practical familiarization with the world of beauty, the world of beauty and new aesthetic needs will cause internal conflicts between the original, true level of the child's aesthetic development.

Second stage: development of aesthetic perception. This stage is aimed at feedback of the perception of the beauty of the environment in children through emotional resonance. During this period, the first aesthetic feelings and emotions appear in children, the first independent thoughts and opinions about art, natural phenomena, processes in society, people's life and behavior are formed.

The third stage is the development of aesthetic ideas, concepts, views, evaluations, judgments and tastes. The initial basis is that the child fills, expands, enriches his knowledge and ideas about the world of beauty, forms his words and phrases, and clarifies his attitude to events and things.

The fourth stage: development of creative aesthetic abilities. At primary school age, imagination, imagination, creative thinking, active development of curiosity, ability to observe,

compare and critically evaluate activities are formed. The child's desire for beauty, the desire for harmony and order occurs.

Aesthetic education is an important element that helps to create a spiritual environment in society, it is a force that shapes and develops human taste and thereby brings a person closer to social relations. Currently, the scope of aesthetic education is expanding. Accordingly, he set himself many important tasks. These are: not only active assimilation of works of art, examples of artistic creativity, but also improvement of the ability to understand and evaluate their aesthetic essence;

- to demonstrate the creative capabilities of the members of the society and to awaken a sense of confidence in being able to use them;

- to develop the skills to relate to the social processes of nature and society with pure feeling and to work diligently to develop them;

- to create a basis for the formation of feelings of national pride and national pride, to awaken a sense of respect for our past spiritual heritage;

- to face the world by developing all types of creativity and encourage them to promote the aspects that are beneficial for the interests of the nation.

The main means of aesthetic education can include such fields as art, information technology, nature, work, and sports. Art is an important tool of aesthetic education. Today, in our society, rather than managing human activity, it is often emphasized that this process should be organized by the person himself. In this process, art has always attracted people as an important tool capable of influencing the feelings of a person. Art penetrates into the world of human passions and feelings, makes them cry, laugh, and think. That's probably why art has always accompanied people. Art is closely connected with the process of education in order to fully express its aesthetic potential. For example, the beautification of human thinking is considered the research object of aesthetics, and the subject of aesthetic education is determined by the aesthetic understanding of the spiritual world by a person. Information technology is a global tool of aesthetic education. Once upon a time, when students of higher education institutions that train specialists in natural and technical fields were asked, "In which fields is your ideal reflected?", most of them said that it is reflected more in the field of art, literature, and enlightenment. It also proves our points that they answered.

It can be said that as a result of information and communication technology becoming an important tool of human and economic development today, people's lifestyle, interaction, and even their appearance have changed radically. Neighborhood is an important tool of aesthetic education. The influence of the aesthetic education of the neighborhood is extremely great. As long as the neighborhood is a small community within the society, today it is of great importance as a place that helps to increase the socio-political activity of an individual and to form his socio-legal culture. Also, the neighborhood is distinguished from other factors by the fact that it can closely influence the refined upbringing of a person. In this respect, the neighborhood, in turn, fulfills the noble goals it has set for itself and educates the modern man in a sophisticated way.

Nature is a necessary means of aesthetic education. It should be specially noted that as much as the family is considered to be the most important factor in the aesthetic development of modern human education, nature is no less important in this process. Because not consciously compromising with nature prevents a person from becoming elegantly perfect. Therefore, it would

not be appropriate to avoid this problem at the moment when the relationship between man and nature is on the brink of crisis and destruction.

Aesthetic competences are formed in children as a result of pedagogically correct organization of work on aesthetic education in the conditions of a general secondary educational institution. The child sufficiently perceives the images and manifestations of beauty in the surrounding world, evaluates the aesthetic value of the studied and observed processes and events, interprets the works of art as a creative process of self-expression of the author.

It should be noted that the aesthetic education of elementary school students is a multi-vector and multi-structural process that is not regulated by time and space boundaries, and it is individual for each child. The educational process is always related to the teacher's creativity, self-expression and professionalism, he (the teacher) leads the child to the world of beauty.

Thus, we can conclude that:

- the main essence of aesthetic education is to form the ability to perceive and understand the beautiful in art and in life, to form aesthetic standards, and to develop creativity in children of primary school age;

- the essence of aesthetic education of elementary school students is the perception and correct understanding of the beautiful in art and life, the development of their aesthetic understanding, taste and ideals, as well as the development of creative inclinations and examples of talent in art. - consists of organizing aesthetic events.

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